

**CHARACTERIZATION AND GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE CHARACTERS
OF JOE AND AMY IN “LITTLE WOMEN” NOVEL WRITTEN BY LOUISE MAY****ALCOTT***Aziza Rashidova**student at Karshi State University***Abstract**

“LITTLE WOMEN” is a classic novel by Louisa May Alcott. The story follows the lives of the four March sisters—Meg, Jo, Beth, and Amy—as they navigate the challenges of adolescence and young adulthood in New England during the Civil War. The novel explores themes of love, family, independence, and the struggle for self-discovery. Through the experiences of the March sisters, Alcott presents a timeless portrayal of female strength, resilience, and the pursuit of personal fulfillment. “LITTLE WOMEN” has captivated readers for generations and continues to be celebrated for its enduring appeal and universal themes. The first part of the novel was published in 1868, the second a year later. The book is about the growing up of four March family sisters during the American Civil War; about his first love, hopes, mutual support, outlook, failures and mistakes. The work became an instant hit and is still the most popular novel for young adults around the world. Over the course of the 20th century, it underwent several adaptations, based on books, plays, operas, and cartoons.

Louisa May Alcott (1832-1888) was an influential American author, best known for her classic novel “Little Women.” Born in Germantown, Pennsylvania, Alcott grew up in a family of transcendentalists and social reformers, which greatly influenced her worldview and her writing. She began writing at an early age to support her family and went on to become a successful and prolific author, publishing numerous novels, short stories, and poems. Alcott’s most famous work, “Little Women,” drew heavily from her own experiences growing up with three sisters and remains a beloved literary classic. The novel’s enduring popularity is a testament to Alcott’s skillful storytelling and her ability to capture the complexities of family dynamics, female identity, and societal expectations. Beyond “Little Women,” Alcott’s writing often explored themes of independence, social justice, and the challenges faced by women in 19th-century America. Her work continues to resonate with readers of all ages and has left a lasting impact on literature and popular culture. In addition to her literary achievements, Alcott was also an advocate for women’s suffrage and an active supporter of abolitionist causes. Her legacy as a writer and social reformer endures, and she is remembered as a trailblazer who used her voice to inspire change and promote the empowerment of women. She got a lot of popularity from her work very quickly. The reason is that

in “Little Women” alone, she highlighted the world view, thinking, behavior and relationships of the women of her time in the image of her family and sisters.

Louise began writing books for teenagers at the request of a publisher in Boston who asked her to write something “for girls”. The writer put the story of his family in the center of the work. The older sister Anna became the prototype of Meg, who showed herself in the image of Joe, but unlike the heroine of the book, she never married.

Young sisters Elizabeth and May are represented in the literary characters

Beth and Amy. The popularity of the work was so weak that it encouraged Louisa to continue the novel. Alcott’s later books, Joe’s Guys, feature the novel’s plot line. A small town, the March family lives. The civil war is raging in the country, but four sisters Meg, Jo, Beth and Amy have not faced the horrors of hostilities, because they live in the north of the United States and the war is being fought in the south. However, everyone echoes it. March family lost a breadwinner – his father, who serves as a priest. In addition, they faced poverty due to the fact that they invested a small amount of money by the head of the family in the enterprise that was bankrupted. He dreams of reminiscing about the happy married days. Now they are forced to live a normal life where they are humiliated for their lives. A constant lack of money causes mental suffering. The novel describes only one year in the life of the girls, but during this time they survive a lot. They meet a young neighbor, Laurie, who becomes a friend of the family and supports them. In addition, the sisters themselves become each other’s support and helpers, they have to fight against negative attitudes and learn life lessons. Master Laurie Mr. Brooke falls in love with Meg and they become engaged. Joe’s manuscript is accepted by the publisher. The girls’ father, Mr. March, becomes seriously ill and the girls’ mother goes to his hospital. Bye raises red flames and barely survives. However, after all the trials, the beloved father finally returns home, and the whole family gathers in front of the fireplace in the evening. The novel is based on the life events of Louis Alcott. Joe is the author’s literary colleague, and Meg, Beth, and Amy are his sisters. The plot of the books is simple – in the center of the story is the poor March family – father and mother (Marmie), the old maid Hannah, 4 daughters of different ages – from 12 to 16 years old – Meg, Jo, Beth, Amy. Their neighbors are wealthy Mr. Lawrence, his 15-year-old grandson Theodore (Lori or Teddy) and his teacher, Mr. Brooke. Each girl is distinguished by her own sweetness and bright character. Meg is a 16-year-old beauty, jealous and jealous of the rich, but thoughtful and hardworking, very feminine, which causes her to be jealous of her wealthy friends. Joe is a 15-year-old boy who writes horror or short stories and loves theatrical effects. He is sharp, angry, calm, but at the same time generous and kind, cheerful and kind. Beth is the ideal person: soft, gentle, flexible, likes to play the piano and kittens, but very shy. Amy, a 12-year-old who loves painting and antique noses, is romantic, loves to show

off, wants to be rich and famous, while learning to control her flaws and know how to please everyone. Although Mrs. March is still the backbone of the main characters in the novel, her mother Marmie, Mrs. Martis, is the backbone of the family. The father – Mr. March – is left behind, but Marmie, we know, is helped by her husband, who has learned to overcome his shortcomings and his wisdom. The spiritual and moral influence of father and mother enables girls to make the right choice whenever they are faced with difficulty, sadness or a difficult decision. More than once, I was amazed at how mother gently encouraged or explained to her daughters some simple but very understandable daily rules for moral and self-development. Despite poverty and limited funds, March's parents always encouraged their daughter's hobbies, so Jo became a good writer (Louise names herself as Jo), Amy tried different art methods and Beth played the piano very well. By her example, Marmie taught the girls charity and patience, although she herself told how difficult it was for her after the loss of her husband's fate. Parents allowed their daughter to do many things, even though they knew they were wrong. And then they trusted the girls to choose their own path, relying on their own inner honesty and never insulted them.

Porters, as working-class individuals, might have a variety of thoughts and perspectives on "Little Women" by Louisa May Alcott. Some porters may relate to the struggles of the March family and find inspiration in the characters' resilience and determination to overcome challenges. They might appreciate the themes of family, love, and the pursuit of personal fulfillment depicted in the novel. Additionally, some porters might admire the strong female characters and their efforts to assert their independence and pursue their ambitions, which could resonate with their own experiences. On the other hand, some porters might view "Little Women" as a portrayal of a lifestyle and social class that is very different from their own, and may not find it relatable to their own experiences. Individuals' thoughts on "Little Women" can vary widely based on their personal experiences and perspectives. For instance, "Like almost every other girl in the world, I fell in love with Little Women ("Mujercitas") as soon as I could read a chapter of the book. In Alcott's pages I escaped from my rather dysfunctional family and my grandfather's somber house, where I spent most of my childhood, and lived with the loving March family. Of course, Jo was my favorite character. This happened in Chile, in the late forties, in an upper-class, narrow-minded, conservative, Catholic, and patriarchal environment, where girls like me were trained from early on for their role as future wives, mothers and proper ladies. I tried to be like Jo: rebellious, capable, independent, brave and caring. I am still trying. (Isabel Allende is the author of A Long Petal of the Sea, which is published in January 2020.)

"In my family, we're three sisters and so Little Women has always felt alive and close. I'm inspired by the relationships between the sisters—their love for each other but also their betrayals.

What can be forgiven? This question from the book has stayed with me, and even inspired my own writing about estranged siblings Michael and Ava. (Haleh Agar is the author of *Out Of Touch*, out on April 2, 2020) Many writers' thoughts on that they see the views expressed in many parts of this work reflect the atmosphere and family relationships of that time. In fact, the most delicate and unique part of the work is the well-formed family environment.

As for the personality, the 4 sisters also have different characters. I tried to give a little description of Joe and Amy that I chose in my article. First of all, if I tell about Ami's character, she is very cute and loves her nose. In fact, although she is sincere, she sometimes fights with Joe and apologizes for her rudeness over her sister. I believe the main reason she married Laurie was that Laurie came from a noble family. Because the situation of the March family was not very good. Girls wanted to marry to rich and noble families. And to Joe it didn't matter. She only wanted to gain popularity behind her works and stories, so she declined Laurie's offer. But in the end, she regrets about her mistake and realizes that happiness is being with the person she loves. But it was too late because Amy and Laurie had already started a family. I don't see how Laurie can marry Amy when he's clearly meant to be with Jo. People are saying Laurie and Jo couldn't have worked out because they are too alike, and is therefore more like brother and sister, but just because two people are similar in many ways doesn't mean they shouldn't be together. It feels as if Laurie's choice of marrying Amy in the end was just settling because he had lost all hope of marrying Jo, it's like part of his soul died when Jo rejected him. Marrying Amy in the end was more like what two lonely people does when they're alone together, they seek comfort in each other and consider it as a mistake in means of love when clearly it was just loneliness plus lack of choice, or as Amy puts it, Laurie pursues Amy simply because she's "second best to Jo." I guess I'll never understand why Alcott decided to pair Laurie with Amy. Laurie and Jo are endgame, they have feelings for each other (Jo had always loved Laurie, she just doesn't want to lose her freedom to marriage, but that doesn't mean there's no spark between the characters) Laurie clearly loves Jo, it's just that the rejection from Jo has shattered his heart so badly, that he no longer cares about what becomes of himself, including who he marries. That's the whole point, Laurie was not the same around Amy as he was with Jo because he naturally always behaved better around Amy, even when they were younger. They become very selfless people around each other. Laurie never harassed Amy, he never wanted her to stop painting so they could get married like he wanted Jo to stop writing, both Amy and Laurie wanted each other so why should he beg for her to be with him? Laurie's advances always made Jo very uncomfortable and he didn't understand the sign yet Amy, after he had gathered his thoughts, was okay with it and reciprocated his feelings. They were on the same page.

Laurie's behavior is really toxic towards Jo, he is possessive of her when in turn he is protective of Amy, is the difference between loving and being in love. Jo was his sister and Amy his lover.

I find Jo's character especially interesting. Perhaps it is because so much of the author's own character is speaking through her or perhaps because she is so human and real in portrayal that she seems almost like a real person. Either way, Jo March, as with other characters such as Scout Finch and Harry Potter, is memorable and timeless. Her boyish inclinations, authorial tendencies and struggles with loneliness, ambition and compromise speak to me profoundly as they have spoken to many others across many generations. (Thoughts on Louisa May Alcott's LITTLE WOMEN <https://medium.com/@benjaminluc/literary-ramblings-weekly-thoughtsand-discussions-d0fd00966f02>)

I know Jo forgives Amy for all this, but I also know that somewhere deep inside, she'll always hold onto it, the fact that Amy married her best friend and boy next door. Anyone who's ever had or met a real-life sister knows: These are complicated relationships, defined by love, yes, but also patterns, wounds, and grudges so deeply ingrained in their psyches that they can never truly let go of them. This is what makes the Jo-Laurie-Amy triangle so good.

The end of Little Women sees its heroine, tomboyish and ambitious Jo, married off to the pointedly unromantic Friedrich Bhaer, a middle-aged and unattractive German professor who disapproves of the sensational stories she writes. And the character readers expect Jo to end up with, her charming best friend Laurie, marries Jo's least favorite sister Amy instead.

References:

1. Little Men (1998) – Plot – IMDb <https://m.imdb.com/title/tt0145048/plotsummary/>
2. Longest, David (1998). Little Women of Orchard House: A Full-length Play. Dramatic Publishing. P. 115. ISBN 0-87129-857-0.
3. Elbert, Sarah (1987). A Hunger for Home: Louisa May Alcott's Place in American Culture. New Brunswick:
 - 4.10 Things You Might Not Know About Little Women <https://www.howlifeunfolds.com/learning-education/10-things-you-mightnot-know-about-little-women>
 5. Isabel Allende is the author of A Long Petal of the Sea, which publishes January 2020.
 6. Haleh Agar is the author of Out Of Touch, out on April 2, 2020

7.Thoughts on Louisa May Alcott's LITTLE WOMEN

<https://medium.com/@benjaminluc/literary-ramblings-weekly-thoughtsand-discussions-d0fd00966f02>

9. Greta Gerwig's Little Women doesn't pretend its marriages are romantic – Vox
<https://www.vox.com/culture/2019/12/27/21037870/little-women-gretagerwig-ending-jo-laurie-amy-bhaer>